

Supplementary information

Development of folate receptor targeting chimeras for cancer selective degradation of extracellular proteins

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Supplementary Figure 1: Uptake of soluble protein targets mediated by FRTACs is dose- and cell line-dependent. **a.** Dose response of anti-FITC-594 (50 nM) uptake induced by FA-FITC and comparison with 50 nM Ab-FA in HepG2 cells for 3 h (n = 3). **B.** Dose response of anti-FITC-594 (50 nM) uptake induced by Ab-FA in HepG2 cells for 3 h (n = 3). **c.** Uptake of anti-biotin-594 (50 nM) in HepG2 cells treated with Ab-FA (25 nM) for 3 h. **d.** Comparison of anti-biotin-594 (50 nM) uptake in different cancer cell lines treated with Ab-FA (25 nM) for 24 h. N indicates biologically independent experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 2: FRTACs generated by two-step labeling method with more FA labeling and longer linker length have higher protein degradation efficiency. **a.** Generation of FRTAC by one-step labeling method. **b.** EGFR degradation mediated by FRTACs prepared by one-step labeling method using different amounts of folate-NHS ester (3x, 12x, and 25x) ($n = 3$). **c.** Comparison of EGFR degradation induced by FRTACs prepared by one- or two-step labeling method with various amounts of reagents ($n = 3$). 3x: 3 molar equivalents, 12x: 12 molar equivalents, 25x: 25 molar equivalents, 1k: PEG1k linker, 2k: PEG2k linker. N3: two-step labeling (12x and 25x indicate the equivalence of the DBCO-NHS ester in the first step; 25 equivalents of folate-azide was used in the second step). NHS: one-step labelling. N indicates biologically independent experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. The statistical significance was assessed using an unpaired two-tailed t-test, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, ns: not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 3: EGFR degradation is related to both FR and EGFR expression levels. **a.** Dose response of EGFR degradation mediated by Ctx-FA (24 h) in HeLa cell ($n = 3$). **b.** Time course of EGFR degradation mediated by Ctx-FA (10 nM) in HeLa cell ($n = 3$). **c.** EGFR degradation mediated by Ctx-FA and negative controls ($n = 3$). **d.** FR1 and FR2 level before and after degrader treatment ($n = 2$). **e.** Endogenous EGFR expression level in different cancer cell lines. **f.** Quantification of **e** ($n = 3$). **g.** EGFR degradation in different cancer cell lines. **h.** Quantification of **g** ($n = 3$). **i.** Quantification of FR expression levels on different cancer cell lines by flow cytometry ($n = 3$). **j.** Correlation of EGFR degradation efficiency with FR expression level alone or the ratio of FR and endogenous EGFR on different cancer cell lines. N indicates biologically independent experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. The statistical significance was assessed using an unpaired two-tailed t-test, ** $P < 0.01$, ns: not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 4: FRTACs mediate the lysosomal degradation of mPD-L1 via their interaction with FR in three mouse cell lines (CT26: c, e, g; B16F10: d, f, h; MOC1: i). **a.** Schematic of Ab3-FA targeting mouse PD-L1 (mPD-L1). **b.** Representative plot of the binding affinity of Ab3 and Ab3-FA to mPD-L1 characterized by MicroScale Thermophoresis (MST) ($n = 2$). **c, d.** Dose response of mPD-L1 degradation (24 h) mediated by Ab3 and Ab3-FA ($n = 3$). **e, f.** Time course of mPD-L1 degradation mediated by Ab3-FA (10 nM) ($n = 3$). **g, h.** Inhibition of Ab3-FA (10 nM) mediated mPD-L1 degradation by free FA (3 mM for CT26, 1 mM for B16F10) and Bafilomycin A1 (BAF, 50 nM) for 24 h ($n = 3$). **i.** Cellular mPD-L1 degradation in MOC1 cells mediated by Ab3-FA (10 nM, 24 h) ($n = 3$). N indicates biologically independent experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. The statistical significance was assessed using an unpaired two-tailed t-test, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, ns: not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 5: Evaluation of the pharmacokinetics (PK) for PD-L1 degraders *in-vivo*. **a.** Representative blot of rat IgG in the plasma of C57BL/6 mice treated with Ab3, Ab3-FA-12x, Ab3-FA-25x at different time points (2.5 mg/kg via IP injection) from 4 mice. **b.** Representative blot of rat IgG in the plasma of C57BL/6 mice bearing B16F10 tumor treated with Ab3-FA-25x at different time points (2.5 mg/kg via IP injection) from 3 mice. Ab3-FA-25x at different concentrations were used as standard. (12x and 25x: 12 or 25 molar equivalents of DBCO-NHS ester in the first step; 25 equivalents of folate-azide were used in the second step). Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 6: Non-targeting FA conjugates and free FA have no effects on tumor growth in CT26 syngeneic mouse model. **a.** Schematic illustration of control treatment in CT26 mouse model. **b.** Tumor growth curves after different treatments as indicated by a. Data are presented as mean \pm SD, $n = 6$ mice. The statistical significance was assessed using a paired t-test, ns: not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 7: FRTAC reveals anti-tumor effect by degrading PD-L1 and recruiting cytotoxic T cell into the tumor. A. Western blot analysis of PD-L1 and CD8a level in tumor tissues isolated from CT26 tumor-bearing mice (7.5 mg/kg daily for 3 days, 3 mice/cohort). **B.** Detection of PD-L1 and CD8 in CT26 tumors by IHC staining (7.5 mg/kg daily for 3 days, 3 mice/cohort). Scale bar: 100 μ m. Representative figures from three mice. Data are presented as mean \pm SD, n=3 mice. The statistical significance was assessed using an unpaired two-tailed t-test, *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 8: FRTACs exhibit cancer selectivity both *in-vitro* and *in-vivo*. **a.** Basal levels of EGFR and PD-L1 in normal HACAT and cancer cell line Huh7 and TU138 (n = 3 biologically independent experiments). **b.** Mouse PD-L1 level in spleen, n = 3 mice. **c.** Mouse PD-L1 level in lung, n = 3 mice. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. The statistical significance was assessed using an unpaired two-tailed t-test, *P < 0.05, ns: not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 9. Characterization of FR expression levels on different cell lines by flow cytometry. **a.** Gating strategies for flow cytometry analysis presented in b, figure 2g and Supplementary Figure 3i. **b.** Representative flow cytometry histogram of FR expression level on different cancer cell lines. n = 10,000 live cells analyzed over three biologically independent experiments.

Supplementary Figure 10a. MALDI-TOF-MS Characterization of Ab (anti-mouse IgG) -FA.

Supplementary Figure 10b. MALDI-TOF-MS Characterization of Ctx-FA generated by one-step labeling.

Supplementary Figure 10c. MALDI-TOF-MS Characterization of Ctx-FA generated by two-step labeling.

Supplementary Figure 10d. MALDI-TOF-MS Characterization of Atz-FA.

Supplementary Figure 10e. MALDI-TOF-MS Characterization of Ab2 (anti-CD47)-FA.

Supplementary Figure 10f. MALDI-TOF-MS Characterization of Ab3 (anti-mouse PD-L1)-FA.

Supplementary Figure 10g. MALDI-TOF-MS Characterization of Rat IgG-FA.

Supplementary Figure 10h. MALDI-TOF-MS Characterization of Human IgG-FA.

Supplementary Table 1. Sources of key reagents and antibodies

Reagents and antibodies	Vendor	Catalog #
DBCO-PEG3-CH ₂ CO-NHS ester	Axis	AP10030
Folic acid-PEG1k-NHS*	Ruixibio	R-1112
Folic acid-PEG2k-NHS*	Ruixibio	R-1112
Folic acid-PEG1k-N ₃ *	Ruixibio	R-8867
Folic acid-PEG2k-N ₃ *	Ruixibio	R-8867
Folic acid-PEG2k-FITC*	Ruixibio	R-8861
AffiniPure Goat Anti-Mouse IgG	Jackson ImmunoResearch	115-005-062
Alexa Fluor® 594 IgG Fraction Monoclonal Mouse Anti-Fluorescein (FITC)	Jackson ImmunoResearch	200-582-037
Anti-Biotin Mouse Monoclonal Antibody (Alexa Fluor®647)	Jackson ImmunoResearch	200-602-211
Anti-Biotin Mouse Monoclonal Antibody (Alexa Fluor®594)	Jackson ImmunoResearch	200-582-211
Mouse Anti-Rabbit IgG Antibody (Alexa Fluor® 647)	Jackson ImmunoResearch	211-605-109
Cetuximab	Selleckchem	A2000
Atezolizumab	Selleckchem	A2004
<i>InVivoPlus</i> anti-mouse PD-L1 (B7-H1)	Bioxcell	BP0101
<i>InVivoMAb</i> anti-human CD47	Bioxcell	BE0019-1
<i>InVivoPlus</i> rat IgG2b isotype control	Bioxcell	BP0090
<i>InVivoMAb</i> human IgG1 isotype control	Bioxcell	BE0297
Rab7 (D95F2) XP® Rabbit mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#9367s
EGF Receptor (D38B1) XP® Rabbit mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#4267s
LAMP1 (D4O1S) Mouse mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#15665s
DYKDDDDK Tag (D6W5B) Rabbit mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#147935s
beta Actin Antibody (C4)	Santa Cruz	sc-47778
Phospho-p44/42 MAPK (Erk1/2) (Thr202/Tyr204) (E10) Mouse mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#9106s
Phospho-EGF Receptor (Tyr1068) (D7A5) XP® Rabbit mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#3777s

PD-L1 (E1L3N®) XP® Rabbit mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#13684s
Recombinant Anti-CD47 antibody	Abcam	ab218810
PD-L1 (D4H1Z) Rabbit mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	60475s
Peroxidase AffiniPure Goat Anti-Rat IgG (H+L)	Jackson ImmunoResearch	112-035-167
PD-L1 (D5V3B) Rabbit mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#64988s
PD-L1/CD274 Polyclonal antibody	Proteintech	17952-1-AP
CD8α (D4W2Z) XP® Rabbit mAb	Cell Signaling Technology	#98941s
FOLR1 Polyclonal antibody	Proteintech	23355-1-AP
FR Antibody (E-11)	Santa Cruz Biotechnology	sc-515521
FOLR2 Polyclonal antibody	Invitrogen	PA5-45768
Goat anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) Alexa Fluor 488	Invitrogen	A11001
Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 594	Invitrogen	A-11012
Anti-rabbit IgG, HRP-linked Antibody	Cell Signaling Technology	#7074s
Anti-mouse IgG, HRP-linked Antibody	Cell Signaling Technology	#7076s
ImmPRESS® HRP Goat Anti-Mouse IgG Polymer Detection Kit, Peroxidase	Vector Laboratories	MP-7452
ImmPRESS® HRP Goat Anti-Rabbit IgG Polymer Detection Kit, Peroxidase	Vector Laboratories	MP-7451
DAPI Solution (1mg/mL)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	62248
Chloroquine diphosphate salt	Sigma-Aldrich	C6628-25G
Bafilomycin A1 Ready Made Solution	Sigma-Aldrich	SML1661
MG132	Selleckchem	S2619
Methyl-β-cyclodextrin	Thermo Fisher Scientific	J66847.06
Chlorpromazine	Thermo Fisher Scientific	J63659.09
Cytochalasin D	Invitrogen	PHZ1063
Folic acid	Sigma-Aldrich	F7876

FOLR1 cDNA ORF Clone, Human, N-DYKDDDDK (Flag®) tag	SinoBiological	HG11241-NF
FOLR2 cDNA ORF Clone, Human, N-DYKDDDDK (Flag®) tag	SinoBiological	HG11219-NF
ON-TARGETplus Human FOLR1 siRNA	Dharmacon	L-010403-00-0005
ON-TARGETplus Human RAB7A siRNA	Dharmacon	L-010388-00-0005
Lipofectamine™ RNAiMAX Transfection Reagent	Thermo Fisher Scientific	13778075

* 1k and 2k refer to the average molecular weight of the PEG (polyethylene glycol) linker.

Supplementary Table 2. Fold change of mean fluorescent intensity (MFI) of FR expression level measured by flow cytometry

	MFI		
	unstained	stained	fold change
HepG2	231	6709	29.04
A549	145	2175	15.00
Cal27	181	5644	31.18
Hela	304	6772	22.28
SW480	116	6199	53.44
Fadu	239	8747	36.60

Supplementary Table 3. Average number of FA labeled on the FRTACs

	Ave. No of FA per antibody
Ab-FA	6.26
NHS_3x (PEG1k)	0.27
NHS_12x (PEG1k)	2.1
NHS_25x (PEG1k)	5.02
NHS_12x (PEG2k)	2.46
NHS_25x (PEG2k)	4.26
N3_12x (PEG1k)	2.89
N3_25x (PEG1k)	5.48
N3_12x (PEG2k)	2.89
N3_25x (PEG2k)	4.85
Atz-FA	4.72
Ab2-FA	3.59
Ab3-FA-12x	2.27
Ab3-FA-25x	5.02
Rat IgG-FA	3.78
Human IgG-FA	5.33